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Esj rmap; EDe w f l rp&d onf ay; urf p e N u M h jz p a o m 'ge \ q e l u s i f b u i¹⁰ jz p j y ð ay; urf o N y s u p ð a l u m i f t n p f t a l u ; r n N /¹¹ rp&d onf p w i n p i n l ; a l u m i f w & m ;¹² ? z h u g ð a e o m & e b l¹³ ? r m & e w \ p p o n i¹⁴ v n f j z p j y ð t v h p h o m p n f p t f s ; f o m w i N t & i f c j z p a o m ' g e u l v m ; j r p f w w a o m a l u m i h p u b q y z g f t a u m i f q k w & m ;¹⁵ v n f j z p j y g o n /

w y # u t b d ' m e l w f & [e f a w m r s m ; E S h y w b o u f i r p & d (5) r s t¹⁶ u l l a t m u f y g t w i f z ö j y x m ; y g o n // , i f w l r f i n -

- (1) t m O g o r p & d
- (2) u k v r p & d
- (3) v m b r p & d
- (4) O P t p & d
- (5) " r p & d w j z p l u o n /

(1) t m O g o r p & d

r t d e & m ? a u s m i f ? t y & m ? a e & m ü O e w l r h j z p l o n / O y r m t m ; j z i h u l l ð a e x l l ð a o m t a q m u f t O ð x l ü o l w p l y g ; v m a & m u ð a e x l l r i u l r u l u j c i f ? v l l f u m ; p ð & m w l M l o l C m a w m r s m ; ? u l l D e a q m i f r e f r r s m ; ? o u l u ð & g f t l r s m ; u m ; a y : w u l v m v S i v l a e & m r z , ð a y ; b l r o c s i ð a , m i ð a q m i b o r s m ; o n l v l] t m O g o r p & d } & b o r s m ; o n j z p l o n / p t m O g o r p & d & b l o n i a o v ð a o m t c g j y w h j z p a e w w l o n / (o l r [k v] o l t t f i & l i u a & m u f w w N /

(2) u k v r p & d

r t d t r s ; E S l u m ' u m r r s m ; u D e w j c i f j z p l o n / r t d q f s ; r w a q u l j z p a p ? ' u m ' u m r r s t u l l j z p a p ? t j c m ; o l C m r s m ; r v m a p v l r q u i q l a p v j c i f y j z p l o n / o l a o m o ' g w & m ; u l l s u f q ð r n h , k v i r m q l & ð ; a o m & [e f r s m ; E S l r q u i q l v j c i f r n r p & d r [k v l y g / p u k v r p & d & b l o n i r t d u m ' u m r w l ü o l r s m ; q u i q l a e o n l u l j r i ð a w l ð a o m t c g O r f x l i y l a v m i ð a v m i j z p l i a o ð t e l w w N / (o l r [k v] a e m i l b o ü v m b l v m b & ð ; y g ; w w l o n /

(3) v m b r p & d

y p i n f v m b l v m b u D e w j c i f j z p l o n / o l w p l y g ; w l l t m ; y p i n f v m b l v m b r & a p v j c i f o a b n j z p l o n / o l a o m & ð a o m v m b l v m b u l r w & m ; o l p e r n l [e f u l f & a p v l b l w & m ; o j z i h o l p h o m & [e f w l u l a p j c i f r n v m b r p & d r [k v l y g / p v m b r p & d & b l o n i r p i l b i f y l i & l i u s w w l i r p i l b i f y l i u l p m ; & w w N /

⁹ r [með 199/ r [með | / 308-9/0ð 5? 183/ O t w a l 2/ 279/

¹⁰ O ð o m O e ð 177/

¹¹ " r p 48/

¹² r ? 1/44/ r ? | ? 1/174/

¹³ r [með 10/ p l v e ð 200/

¹⁴ p l v e ð 104/

¹⁵ o l l # ð 1/ 126/

¹⁶ w y l d ' m e l w f 16/ 107/ t l l 3/ 25/ t b a l y k 122/

(4) OP&d

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(5) "rP&d

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¹⁷ r? 1? 19? 43-4/

¹⁸ r[me& 10? 198/

¹⁹ pV& 59/

²⁰ w&lyd'mel y0*f-w&16? 107/

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 "ry' t | uxm(yxr)/ (1957)/ &efule! omoema&00p0XmeyE0y0wlu0/
 "ry' t | uxm('kvd)/ (1957)/ &efule! omoema&00p0XmeyE0y0wlu0/
 ayw0wkt | uxm('kvd)/ (1957)/ &efule! omoema&00p0XmeyE0y0wlu0/
 Zmwu | uxm (yXar mbma*g)/ (1957)/ &efule! omoema&00p0XmeyE0y0wlu0/
 r[med' ot | uxm/ (1999)/ &efule! omoema&00p0XmeyE0y0wlu0/

#lumusrsm

Orwā 2 - Orwā dāem' e#lum(' kvd)

r? #0 1 - rivyPño#lum(yxr)

o# #0 1 - o*gxmo*#lum (yxr)

tjcmusrsm

ObmObd- tbd'rwθbmbd

wy'd'mef- wy#utbd'mef

y#utbd'mef - y#utbd'mef

tbd'rmoi fweſ - tbd'rmoi fweſ

taxaxusrsm

Og, mrom&(t&ſ)/ (2003)/ *[[tbd'rmytp0]]* / &eulefrll omoema&OelluDXme/

rifwifēſ (a' guivm)/ (2001)/ *[[AK tbd'rmtEpcy]]*? pwkw-tLut/ &eulefrll jrrēſ &wempmtlywlu/